

A new oleanolic acid saponin from *Achyranthus aspera*

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Butanol extract of *Achyranthus aspera* inflorescence afforded a new compound which was characterized as β -D-fucopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 4)-(β -D-glucopyranosyluronic acid)-(1 \rightarrow 3)-oleanolic acid.

Achyranthus aspera L. (Amaranthaceae) is distributed widely in India as an annual weed. The plant is diuretic, purgative, antidote against snake bite¹. Seeds are emetic¹ and used against renal dropsy². The plant extract is also used as abortifacient and contraceptive³. Presence of ecdysterone in its roots causes insect molting activity⁴. A few saponins of oleanolic acid in addition to aliphatic compounds and betaine have been reported in the plant⁵. In this communication we describe the structure of a new glycoside of oleanolic acid.

Results and Discussion

The saponin **1** was obtained by column chromatography of *n*-butanol fraction. Their IR spectrum exhibited broad absorption bands at 3450 and 1040 cm^{-1} for OH group indicating its glycosidic nature. On acid hydrolysis, compound **1** afforded oleanolic acid, structure of which was confirmed by spectral analysis⁶ and a direct comparison with authentic sample (co-TLC), as aglycone part. The sugars were analyzed using HPLC with RI detector and confirmed as glucuronic acid and fucose. Thus, the molecular formula was suggested as $\text{C}_{42}\text{H}_{66}\text{O}_{13}$. Its EI mass lacks M^+ but afforded peak at m/z 439 due to loss of glucuronic acid and fucose from compound **1**. The positive ion FAB-MS showed pseudomolecular ion peak at m/z 801 $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ which is in good agreement with the molecular formula $\text{C}_{42}\text{H}_{66}\text{O}_{13}$. The presence of fucose as terminal sugar was confirmed by its detection on partial hydrolysis of **1**.

The proton noise-decoupled ^{13}C NMR spectrum of **1** displayed 42 carbon resonances. The number of attached hydrogen to each carbon was determined by the DEPT technique which suggested the presence of $8 \times \text{CH}_3$, $10 \times \text{CH}_2$, $15 \times \text{CH}$ and 9 quaternary carbon atoms. The appearance of two anomeric carbon signals at δ 107.1 and 103.0 was in accordance with the presence of a disaccharide moiety in **1**. The anomeric carbon signals above 100 ppm suggested the glycosidation site at alcohol and not the acid group. Deshielding of C-4 signal of glucuronic acid supported 1 \rightarrow 4 linkage of glucuronic acid with fucose.

The ^1H NMR spectrum displayed signals caused by seven tertiary methyl groups (δ 0.77, 0.90, 0.95, 0.96, 0.99, 1.24 and 1.29), one olefinic proton [δ 5.45 (brd s)] and two anomeric protons [δ 5.01(d, J 8 Hz) and 4.88 (d, J 8 Hz)] suggesting the glycosidation⁷ in **1** with OH and not with COOH. The C-3 proton of genin appeared at δ 3.29 as double doublet. Thus compound **1** was identified as β -D-fucopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 4)-(β -D-glucopyranosyluronic acid)-(1 \rightarrow 3)-oleanolic acid. ^{13}C NMR data of **1** (Table 1) were also consistent with the structure.

Experimental

M.ps. were determined on a Electrothermal 1A 9000 apparatus and are uncorrected. Optical rotation was measured on a Jasco DIP-181 polarimeter. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker FTNMR using TMS as internal standard, IR spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 1710 spectrophotometer, and EIMS on a Jeol-JMSD-3000 instrument whereas the positive ion mode FABMS on a Jeol SX 102/DA-6000, mass spectrometer/Data system using argon/xenon (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas and accelerating voltage of 10 kV with *m*-nitrobenzyl alcohol as matrix. Column chromatography was carried out on silica gel (B.D.H., 60–120 mesh), TLC on Merck readymade $^{60}\text{F}_{254}$ plate. Spots were visualized by exposure to iodine vapor and by spraying with 10% H_2SO_4 , followed by heating at 110 $^\circ$.

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Table 1. ^{13}C NMR spectral shifts of 1

Aglycone part		Sugar part	
Carbon no.		Carbon no.	
1	38.6	1'	107.1
2	26.6	2'	72.8
3	89.4	3'	77.2
4	39.5	4'	82.0
5	55.7	5'	75.8
6	18.7	6'	171.0
7	33.2	1''	103.0
8	39.8	2''	71.5
9	48.0	3''	72.6
10	37.0	4''	74.6
11	23.8	5''	69.9
12	122.6	6''	18.5
13	144.9		
14	42.2		
15	28.1		
16	23.8		
17	46.7		
18	42.0		
19	46.5		
20	31.0		
21	34.3		
22	33.3		
23	28.3		
24	17.0		
25	15.5		
26	17.4		
27	26.2		
28	180.3		
29	33.2		
30	23.8		

High performance liquid chromatography of sugars was performed on a Shimadzu LC-10A instrument with RI detector.

The inflorescences of *A. aspera* were collected locally from Lucknow, identified in our Botany Department and a voucher specimen deposited in the herbarium of this Institute.

Isolation of compound : The shade dried and powdered inflorescence (3 kg) were extracted with ethanol ($5 \times 5 \text{ dm}^3$) at room temperature and the combined extract was concentrated to 500 ml and then H_2O (500 ml) added. The aqueous

ethanol solution was then fractionated to give hexane, chloroform and butanol soluble fractions. The butanol extract (65 g) was chromatographed over silica gel (1200 g) and eluted successively with chloroform and chloroform-methanol mixtures of increasing polarity. The fractions obtained from $\text{CHCl}_3\text{-MeOH}$ (80 : 20) yielded compound 1 (630 mg), m.p. 202–204°, R_f 0.58 ($\text{CHCl}_3\text{-MeOH}$, 85 : 15), $[\alpha]_D - 3^\circ$ (CHCl_3).

β -D-Fucopyranosyl-(1→4)-(β-D-glucopyranosyluronic acid)-(1→3)-oleanolic acid (1) : Colourless crystals (630 mg), m.p. 202–204°, R_f 0.58, ($\text{CHCl}_3\text{-MeOH}$, 85 : 15), $[\alpha]_D - 3^\circ$ (CHCl_3); ν_{max} 3450, 2870, 1700, 1460, 1385, 1040, 760 cm^{-1} ; FABMS m/z 801 $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$; PMR ($\text{C}_5\text{D}_5\text{N}$, 300 MHz) δ 0.77, 0.90, 0.95, 0.96, 0.99, 1.24, 1.29, (7 × CH_3 , s), 1.69 (CH_3 , d, 6 Hz, fuc), 5.01 (1H, m, fuc H-1), 4.56 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, fuc H-2), 3.76 (2H, m, fuc H-3,5), 4.23 (1H, m, fuc H-4), 4.88 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, glc A H-1), 4.04 (1H, t, J 6 Hz, glc A H-2), 4.37 (1H, m, glc A H-3), 4.66 (1H, d, J 6 Hz, glc A H-4), 4.74 (1H, m, glc A H-5), 3.29 (1H, dd, J 9 Hz, 6 Hz, genin H-3), 5.45 (1H, br s, genin H-12); ^{13}C NMR ($\text{C}_5\text{D}_5\text{N}$, 75 MHz) : see Table 1.

Acid hydrolysis of 1 : Saponin 1 (100 mg) was refluxed with 5% H_2SO_4 (10 ml) on a water-bath for 4 h. The usual work up of the reaction mixture afforded oleanolic acid, m.p. 306–308°, MS m/z 456, confirmed by comparison with authentic oleanolic acid (m.p., m.m.p., co-TLC, MS, NMR).

Identification of sugar moieties of 1 : The aqueous layer separated after the removal of oleanolic acid was neutralized with barium carbonate, filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure. The residue obtained was subjected to HPLC using mobile phase acetonitrile-water (80 : 20), carbohydrate column (water), (250 × 4.5 mm I.D., 4 μm), at the flow rate of 1 ml/min and a RI detector (Shimadzu). The sugar were identified as D-glucuronic acid (R_f 4.2) and D-fucose (R_f 6.44) by co-comparison with authentic sugars.

Partial acid hydrolysis of 1 : Saponin 1 (40 mg) was hydrolyzed with 1% H_2SO_4 for 10 min. The neutralized and concentrated aqueous hydrolysate showed the presence of fucose only.

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